

Emotion Cum False Information Detection Based on Sentiment, Structural and Semantic Frameworks

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Abstract—The existence of false information in Online Social Networks (OSNs) can pose a serious threat to the ecology of social information dissemination, and this statement can arouse netizen’s feelings of fear and sadness and affect their social, mental, and physical health. Many researchers focus on emerging problems related to detecting false information and investigating the emotional framing of misinformation in social media. However, detecting false information combined with examining public emotion dynamics over temporal social interaction needs to be fully explored. To tackle this problem, we propose a fusion model called Emotion-based False Information Detection (Emo-FID). The model develops using Sentiment/Emotion, Semantic, and Structural (3S) frameworks of information propagation in a social network context. The proposed model performed both false information detection tasks as well as systematically predicted public emotions by understanding the propagation pattern contained in a social network context. The ultimate goal of the proposed framework is to classify public emotions and detect rumour/non-rumour conversations by adopting the Bi-GCN, GRU and BERT methods. To understand the effectiveness of the proposed approach, we conduct extensive experiments on publicly available real-world Twitter (currently known as X) datasets covering different events. The experimental results indicate that our fusion model performs well and achieves state-of-the-art accuracy on existing datasets.

Index Terms—emotion classification, false information detection, social networks, neural networks

I. INTRODUCTION

In the age of Online Social Networks (OSNs), automatic false information, fake news detection, and fact extraction have attracted increasing attention worldwide. False information can be categorised in various forms such as fabricated, propaganda, conspiracy theories, hoaxes, biased or one-sided rumours, clickbait and satire news [1]. These various forms of false information mislead people to make unjust decisions in sensitive circumstances. The extensive dissemination of false information related to public health, politics, and disasters affects modern society in various ways. In this regard, several studies [2]–[4] show different observations of political contents, conspiracy news, and public health-related misinformation that significantly affect people’s day-to-day social activities, lifestyles, and so on. For example, recent events have witnessed a massive growth in research on detecting fake news and false information due to the global pandemic [5].

Consequently, the enormous spreading of an “infodemic” of health misinformation and cybercrime in the COVID-19 crisis in social network platforms became a global enemy that misled people to accept fake beliefs such as misinformation about vaccination against COVID-19 [6]. This statement misled citizens and forced them to distrust governments, researchers, and medical personnel, causing some disruption in the global fight. Therefore, there is an urgent need for an effective false information detection method.

Despite the complex situation worldwide, these social media outlets are experiencing and presenting different views and opinions, and as a result, they affect readers’ emotions during various outbreak-related incidents [7]. False information is created to evoke emotional responses in readers that can lead to specific behaviours and benefit the creator [8]. Emotional contagion paired with false information intentionally misguides the public by disseminating social media postings. Emotions are indeed regarded as a dominant driver of human behaviour, and understanding the role of emotions in spreading false information is crucial for developing effective strategies to combat their negative impact on social media [9]. False information infused with strong emotional elements such as fear, outrage, or excitement are more likely to be shared and spread rapidly across social networks. In this regard, Zaeem et al. [10] observed the significant association between negative sentiment with fake news and positive sentiment with true news. False information concerning health has particularly severe consequences on people’s quality of life and even risk of mortality. This online fake statement can manipulate the emotions of netizens, and it can impact social-mental-physical health [3]. It depicts that people are surrounded by triangle disorder (*Social*∠*Mental*∠*Physical*). Hence, tracking people’s emotions on false information can play a major role for the people, decision-makers and health practitioners to find trustworthy sources as well as reliable guidance when they need it.

In addition to understanding emotional relationships in disseminating false information, capturing internal and external influence plays an important role in social networks. With the adaptation of social identity theory and by grouping different psychological factors as an internal influence, researchers

[11] discuss how the external influence on individuals can contribute to their unintentional spreading of fake news. Therefore, to investigate the behavior of netizens with regard to false information, we have analyzed the users' internal and external emotional influence factors. To improve the performance of the rumor detection model, investigating temporal dynamic structure with emotional information [12] and extracting semantic features of information propagation contained in social network texts is a very important task [13]. As a part of this research, the researchers [14] have studied the interplay between emotions, information diffusion dynamics, and user behaviour to devise interventions aimed at promoting critical thinking, media literacy, and responsible sharing practices. Therefore, detecting of false information and systematically examining public emotions by understanding its propagation patterns is a significant problem to explore.

Research on false information or fake news is performed in two broad areas: technical and behavioral [15]. Technical research focus on detecting fake news automatically using Natural Language Processing (NLP) methods [16], [17] and pre-trained language models such as Bidirectional Encoder Representations from Transformers (BERT) [18], RoBERTa [19], while behavioral research focuses on human aspects like belief, attitude, intentions, etc to understand the impact of false claims on the formation of opinions [20]. In this paper, our study focuses on combining both technical and behavioral research where we detect false information by using a pre-trained language model and also understanding public emotion on false information.

In technical research, the existing method of false information or fake news has some limitations, such as (i) ignoring the actual meaningful context at the time of extracting features from the text data, (ii) being incapable of integrating the effects of emotion dynamics and information diffusion information as an implicit feature. In the behavioral research, the existing works have been implemented based on internal and external influential methods by adopting social identity theory [21]. However, they need to be more capable of integrating the effects of the long-term historical information users. Because in social networks, people continuously receive relevant information from their neighbours and update their previous beliefs. For example, significant work [22] has been conducted by capturing historical influence and personal and neighbour opinions within social discourse to better understand opinion behaviors. However, to the best of our knowledge, systematically understanding personal and social influential patterns with dynamic emotion detection over rumour/non-rumour has not yet been explored. On the other hand, it is also essential to capture the user's historical influential pattern in order to understand the dynamic nature of the conversation. Moreover, the combination of technical and behavioral research still needs to be explored properly.

To address these gaps, we introduce a fusion model by integrating emotional information with semantic and structural features, namely *Emotion-based False Information Detection* (Emo-FID). The proposed model detect the rumour/non-

rumour and employ it for emotion prediction. Taking advantage of the neural network, we employed Gated Recurrent Units (GRUs) to analyse the user's emotion by tracking through personal, interpersonal and historical information of communication. In order to obtain semantic features, we used the BERT pre-training model. The proposed model also obtains structural features of propagation by using Bi-directional Graph Convolutional Networks (Bi-GCNs). The purpose of this work is to identify users' future emotions and false information by systematically examining different influential features along with emotional ones and their temporal propagation patterns. The effectiveness of the proposed approach is demonstrated by analysing different topics on publicly available Twitter (currently known as X) datasets. The contributions of this paper can be summarized as:

- We develop a fusion model for detecting false information as well as the emotions of the user by integrating sentiment, semantic and temporal dynamic structure.
- To understand the dynamic nature of emotional influential patterns, we consider four crucial factors, i.e., (i) prior neighbouring influence, (ii) prior personal influence, (iii) current neighbouring influence, and (iv) historical influence at each timestamp.
- We concatenate temporal dynamics structure and emotional information using Bi-GCNs, the GRUs model, and semantic information extracted by BERT to achieve superior results on the real-world social media dataset.

The rest of the paper is organized as follows: A related work is presented in Section II. In Section III, we described the research methodology, including the implementation details. Afterwards, we discuss data analysis and experimental results in Section IV, and finally, we draw conclusions in Section V.

II. RELATED WORK

The research in false information, fake news and/or rumours detection is gaining attention due to its devastating consequences. Many researchers have used high-level methods, techniques, and features to detect false information. Liu et al. [9] show the detection approaches mainly contain three components, i.e., the *datasets* used for development, the *methods* used for execution and the *features* used within these methods. According to Guo et al. [23], the type of features used in existing false information detection methods divided into four categories: content-based methods, social context-based methods, feature fusion-based methods, and deep learning-based methods. A large body of research focuses on improving processing efficiency by combining several methods from multiple directions to improve the detection efficiency of false information. For instance, Zhou and Zafarani [24] show a study of fake news has four perspectives: knowledge-based, style-based, propagation-based, and credibility-based. In addition to the above-mentioned approaches, methods and features of improving false information detection, researchers are using other improvement ideas, such as multimodal technology combined with visual image information and textual emotion

recognition technology to detect news content combined with sentiment analysis [19].

In many studies, sentiment and/or emotion information is fused with other features such as semantic, propagation and diffusion to maximize detection performance. Recently, many advanced fusion methods have been used to carry out learning within the context of a single or multitask framework. Therefore, in this section, we exclusively introduce the different advanced fusion techniques as well as sentiment/emotion with semantic, and propagation structure features for false information detection.

Recently, Zhao et al. [25] proposed a multi-domain fake news detection framework based on a pre-trained representation embedding module, and a collaborative module involves training multiple neural networks based on TextCNNs. The author applied BERT and Contrastive Language-Image Pretraining (CLIP) [26] text encoders combined as fusion embedding for pre-trained image-text paired datasets and aims to take advantage of the rich semantic representations obtained through state-of-the-art (SOTA) multimodal learning. Another work has been presented by Kelk et al. [27], where they developed *EmoAttention* a BERT model architecture using emotional and snippet attention layers to verify the truth of political claims, supported by evidence from Google news snippets. Interestingly, another combined model called FakeFlow was proposed by Ghanem et al. [28], who designed a model that detects fake news articles by taking into account the flow of affective information. The proposed architecture contains two modules: a Convolutional Neural Network (CNN) is used to extract topic-based information and another Bidirectional Gated Recurrent Units (Bi-GRUs) is used to extract affective information. Similarly, Ghanem et al. [29] proposed an Emotionally Infused Network (EIN) based on two branches where a word embedding layer is used, followed by a Long short-term memory (LSTM) layer in the content-based feature and five emotional resources are used to extract the emotional features. Most recent advanced fusion or combined methods have significantly improved the detection accuracy and adopted pre-trained models to represent text data and image data, but they ignore the semantic context of the text. As a result, it's hard to express effectively and accurately the meaning of the text, which has a significant impact on the detection rate of the model.

Besides, the temporal dynamics structure or propagation information over time and semantic features are also effective indicators for detecting false information. For example, Wang et al. [12] present an end-to-end rumour detection model that effectively represents the temporal dynamics structure by using GRU and extraction of sentiment by using the BERT model. In a recent study by Fang et al. [30], the authors propose a Propagation Tree Variational AutoEncoder (ptVAE) model for rumour detection by Sentiment pattern in propagation and propagation characteristics. On the other hand, Zhang et al. [19] proposed a Graph Attention Networks (GATs) based model for fake news detection that combines sentence semantics through entity representation, and sentiment fusion

between sentences to fully utilize sentiment interaction features. A similar study was conducted by Zhang et al. [13], where the BERT model is used to extract the semantic feature, a Bi-GRU+Attention model is used to extract the sentiment feature, and Bi-GCN networks are used to extract propagation information. Most of the works make full use of semantic information, sentiment features, and propagation structure but do not consider the role of emotional influence features along with the user's historical influence information. In this study, we have captured the role of emotional changes, semantic information and the propagation structure along with the user's emotional influential factors.

III. METHODOLOGY

To alleviate the limitations of rumour detection as well as emotion classification, we have formulated the fusion model by combining emotional information, temporal dynamics structure and semantic information in social networks. In this section, we firstly formulate the classification and the rumour detection problem by introducing some key notions. Finally, we describe the details components of our Emo-FID model (Fig. 1) for false detection and emotion classification.

A. Problem Formulation

In online social networks, users can share information by posting a tweet. Other users (neighbours) can further retweet, reply or like the tweet. Here, we define the content, user-based features, and emotional features for the study. Moreover, we consider information propagation as the response between posts over time.

1) *Definition (Emotional-based Feature) [F1]:* The emotional lexicons are annotated based on the well-known Russell's circumflex model of affect [31] where core affect map identified sixteen states ($R_u(i) \in \{1, 2, 3, \dots, 16\}$). To reduce the number of emotional states, we consider four quadrants defined in Russell's model and named them as *excitement* ($R1$), *contentment* ($R2$), *depression* ($R3$), and *distress* ($R4$). We have adopted well-grounded emotional lexicons to increase the coverage of the text such as ANEW [32], EmoLex [33] etc.

2) *Definition (Content-based Feature) [F2]:* The content feature contains data (e.g. words, URLs, hashtags, emoticons) and meta-data (e.g. tweet, reply, repost, like) related to it. We analyse this feature by choosing different properties here: the length of tweets, the number of words, uppercase characters, punctuation characters, stemmers, first/second-order pronouns, adverbs, hashtags, URLs, containing question marks, exclamation marks, at the rate sign etc.

3) *Definition (User-based Feature) [F3]:* The user feature is referred to as the attributes explored within social network analysis threads that facilitate user interactions. As part of this feature, we consider properties such as seven common features that describe the attributes of the user, such as the number of followers, number of friends, followers-friends ratio, the number of historical tweets, number of historical comments, number of historical favourites and verified user account.

Fig. 1. General view of Emo-FID model

4) *Definition (Temporal Propagation Framework)*: In the temporal propagation framework, every participating user's data is defined by the sequence of *outgoing* and *incoming* tweets arranged in the order of posting time. The *outgoing* tweets are those tweets posted by the target user about the topic/event under consideration. Whereas, the *incoming* tweets are those tweets posted by neighbours about target topic, and are received by the user through meta-data from *content-based feature* [F2] (e.g. tweet, reply, repost and like).

B. Emotion-based False Information Detection (Emo-FID) Model

The ultimate goal of the proposed framework is to classify public emotions and detect rumour/non-rumour conversations by adopting the Bi-GCNs, GRUs and BERT methods. Fig. 1 illustrates the overall architecture of the proposed model, which is categorized into four components, namely *feature-based temporal propagation framework*, *emotion-based user influential framework*, *semantic feature extraction framework*

and *emotion classification and false information detection*. All components are connected to three layers, i.e., the input layers, the fusion layer and the output layers. First, the input layer obtains the user’s personal/interpersonal opinion, a set of tweets’ words and an adjacency matrix representing the tweets’ temporal propagation structure. Second, the Bi-GCNs, GRUs, and BERT models are used in the network topology of information propagation, the corresponding emotionally influential information, and the embedding layer to serialize the tweet text. In the fusion layer, the concatenating operation is performed by obtaining feature vectors. Finally, the output layer is passed through the *Softmax* function for rumour/non-rumour detection and emotion classification.

1) *Feature-based Temporal Propagation Framework*: To effectively study emotional influence and behavioural impact on social media, we have formulated *feature-based temporal propagation framework* based on temporal conversation and different emotion states of the user by identifying three distinct features, i.e., *emotional-based features [F1]*, *content-based features [F2]* and *user-based features [F3]*.

Given a direct graph $G = (V, E)$, where each vertex $u \in V$ represents a user and each edge $(u, v) \in E$ represents a user u following to another user v . The each user $u \in V$, his/her posting sequence contains $PS_u = \langle M_u(i), S_u(i), t_u(i) \rangle$ where a tweet message $M_u(i)$ with emotion state $S_u(i)$ at time $t_u(i)$ posted by u . Taken into account G , we considered a collection of all external set for each user $u \in V$, which denoted as a $Z_u = \{v | (u, v) \in E\}$. The size of the neighbour set Z_u is $n(u)$. In addition, $A_i \in \{0, 1\}^{n_k \times n_k}$ is an adjacency matrix.

For every participating u ’s data, we have estimated the *incoming* tweets posted by v that the user u has received between the time of two consecutive *outgoing* tweets is referred to as t_0 and t_1 . Additionally, we also include the incoming tweets posted by v before posting u ’s first tweet at time t_0 . Given a user u , as we construct a typical temporal tweet chain or tuple chain of u ’s posted a message at each timestamp $t_u(i)$, where \downarrow denotes (incoming) tweets and \uparrow denotes the (outgoing) tweets.

$u = \langle \dots, \downarrow M_{t_{0-1}}^C \rangle, \uparrow M_{t_0}^C, \langle \downarrow M_{t_{0+1}}^C, \dots \rangle, \uparrow M_{t_1}^C, \langle \downarrow M_{t_{1+1}}^C, \dots \rangle, \uparrow M_{t_2}^C, \dots$ where the user u posts his first tweet at t_0 denoted by the tuple $\uparrow M_{t_{0-i}}^C, i = 1, 2, \dots$ and $C \in \{tweet, reply, repost\}$. Similarly, incoming tweets between the Z_u ’s tweets are denoted by the tuple $\langle \downarrow M_{t_{k+0}}^C, \downarrow M_{t_{k+1}}^C, \dots \rangle$.

With the adaptation of this framework, we deploy *user-based features [F3]* and Bi-GCNs [34] from the social conversation to extract temporal propagation information for rumour detection from both forward-backwards and backwards-forward operations. The core idea of GCNs is to apply a convolution operation on graphs by aggregating information from a node’s local neighbourhood. This allows each node to update its features based on its neighbours’ features. In the process of propagation and diffusion feature extraction, each sequence constructs a propagation structure based on (outgoing) and (incoming) relationship. We employ a

novel DropEdge [35] method as a random edge deletion technology to reduce over-fitting for GCN-based models during the training state. Formally, suppose the total number of edges in the graph A is N_e and the dropping rate is p , then the adjacency matrix after DropEdge, A' , is computed as below:

$$A' = A - A_{drop} \quad (1)$$

where A_{drop} is a matrix structure randomly sampled from the original edge set using $N_e \times p$. At each training epoch, p percentage of edges are dropped via Eq. (1) to form A' , which avoid penitential over-fitting issues. In our Bi-GCNs model, we construct two network components: a Forward Chain Graph Convolutional Networks (FC-GCNs) and a Backward Chain Graph Convolutional Networks (BC-GCNs). For FC-GCNs, the adjacency matrix is represented as $A^{FC} = A'$, while for BC-GCNs, the adjacency matrix is $A^{BC} = A'$. The FC-GCNs and the BC-GCNs obtain the propagation and diffusion features, respectively. The equation of the FC-GCNs is as follows:

$$HL^{(FC)} = \sigma(A^{FC} \times W^{FC}) \quad (2)$$

where $HL^{(FC)} \in R^{n \times v}$ is the hidden layer feature, W^{FC} is the filter parameter matrix of FC-GCNs, σ is the ReLU activation function, and the equation of the BC-GCNs is as follows:

$$HL^{(BC)} = \sigma(A^{BC} \times W^{BC}) \quad (3)$$

where $HL^{(BC)} \in R^{n \times v}$ is the hidden layer feature, W^{BC} is the filter parameter matrix of BC-GCNs. The representations of propagation and diffusion are the aggregations from the node representations of FC-GCNs and BC-GCNs, respectively. Here, we employ mean-pooling operators to aggregate information from these two sets of node representations. It is formulated as follows:

$$\hat{HL}^{(FC)} = MEAN(HL^{(FC)}) \quad (4)$$

$$\hat{HL}^{(BC)} = MEAN(HL^{(BC)}) \quad (5)$$

Finally, after obtaining the feature vectors for the FC-GCNs and BC-GCNs, we concatenate the representations of propagation and the representation of dispersion to merge the information as follows:

$$H'(l) = concat(\hat{HL}^{(FC)}, \hat{HL}^{(BC)}) \quad (6)$$

2) *Emotional-based User Influential Framework*: In this section, we have constructed an influential framework based on GRUs along with *emotional-based features [F1]*, which has the ability to capture user’s historical information. All the incoming set of emotion tweets from neighbour are denoted by the tuple $\langle \downarrow R_{t_{k+0}}^C, \downarrow R_{t_{k+1}}^C, \dots \rangle$ and fall between the user’s personal emotion tweets $\uparrow R_{t_k}^C$ and $\uparrow R_{t_{k+1}}^C$.

$u = \langle \dots, \downarrow R_{i,t_{0-1}}^C \rangle, \uparrow R_{i,t_0}^C, \langle \downarrow R_{i,t_{0+1}}^C, \dots \rangle, \uparrow R_{i,t_1}^C, \langle \downarrow R_{i,t_{1+1}}^C, \dots \rangle, \uparrow R_{i,t_2}^C, \dots$

At each time stamp, four crucial emotion influence factors are consider for shaping one’s future dynamics emotion, i.e., prior neighbouring influence $PN_{u,i}(t)$, prior personal

influence $PP_{u,i}(t)$, current neighbouring influence $CN_{u,i}(t)$ and historical emotion influence $HI_{u,i}(t)$. Therefore, future emotion state $S_u(i)$ is classified at the next timestamp t_u based on personal emotion sequence $\uparrow PR_{u,i}(t) = \langle \uparrow R_{i,t_0}^C \dots, \uparrow R_{i,t_k}^C \rangle$ sent by the user u at t and all the neighbouring emotion of the messages $\downarrow NR_{u,i}(t) = \langle \downarrow R_{i,t_0-1}^C \dots, \downarrow R_{i,t_k}^C \rangle$ received from $t-1$ to t . To proposed the sequential influence model, we already taken place personal and neighbouring emotion influence, i.e., derived by $X_{u,i}(t) \in \langle PN_{u,i}(t), PP_{u,i}(t), CN_{u,i}(t) \rangle$. To update u 's next emotion at $t_u(i+1)$, the historical emotion influence $HI_{u,i}(t-1)$ could be replaced by the temporal internal emotion state $C_{u,i}(t-1)$. In our sequential influence model, we acknowledge the GRUs, which is more effective and compact for dropping irrelevant information and updating the relevant information with affordable computation cost. This unit is formally expressed as follows:

$$[r_{u,i}(t) = \sigma(W_r[C_{u,i}(t-1), X_{u,i}(t)] + b_r) \quad (7)$$

$$[g_{u,i}(t) = \sigma(W_g[C_{u,i}(t-1), X_{u,i}(t)] + b_g) \quad (8)$$

$$\tilde{C}_{u,i}(t) = \tanh(W_c[[r_{u,i}(t) \cdot C_{u,i}(t-1), X_{u,i}(t)] + b_c) \quad (9)$$

$$C_{u,i}(t) = [g_{u,i}(t) \cdot \tilde{C}_{u,i}(t) + (1 - [g_{u,i}(t)]) \cdot C_{u,i}(t-1) \quad (10)$$

where, $W_r, W_g, W_c \in R^{c \times d_w}$, and $b_r, b_g, b_c \in R^c$ and d_w is the dimension of emotion state region. The reset gate $[r_{u,i}(t)$ determines how much past information forget, i.e., not relevant for the future. The update gate $[g_{u,i}(t)$ helps the model to determine how much of the past information needs to process for the future. These are two important gates which decide what information should be passed to the output and its' control long-term and short-term memory accordingly. The current memory content gate $\tilde{C}_{u,i}(t)$ which will use the reset gate to store the relevant information from the past. The final gate used to calculate the internal emotion state $C_{u,i}(t)$ which holds information for the current unit and passes it down to the network. In order to do that the update gate is needed. It determines what to collect from the current memory content $\tilde{C}_{u,i}(t)$ and what from the previous steps $C_{u,i}(t-1)$, as mention on equation 10.

3) *Semantic Feature Extraction Framework*: In this proposed framework, we have used word embedding (*content-based feature [F2]*) and employed a BERT to extract semantic feature information. The multi-head self-attention mechanism of the BERT model significantly resolves the issue of ignoring meaningful context and extracted feature vectors which accurately represent the literal meaning of the text.

The length n of tweet content is represented as a set of words $Q = \{w_1, w_2, \dots, w_n\}$, where w_i is the i^{th} keyword of the text and the corresponding feature vector set $K = \{v_1, v_2, \dots, v_n\}$ is obtained through the BERT pre-processing model, where v_i is the word vector corresponding to the feature word w_i . The initialized text word vectors are submitted to the Transformer model to extract features. The Transformer encoder comprises multiple identical layers, each containing

two sub-layers: a multi-head attention mechanism and a feed-forward neural network. The attention mechanism assigns a weight to each word vector to learn the internal dependencies and to extract the text sequence's internal structural features. The feature vector $(Q, K) \in T$ learned by the multi-headed self-attention layer to fed the feed-forward neural network, and the learned tweet semantic representation vector F_u is obtained as follows:

$$F_u(i) = \max(0, TW_a + b_a) \quad (11)$$

where W_a and b_a are the corresponding weight matrix and bias terms of the feed-forward neural network.

4) *Emotion Classification and False Information Detection*: For the purpose of significantly detecting rumour/non-rumour $Y_u(i)$ and u 's future emotion state $S_u(i)$, we formulate the problem as a predicting probability distribution by given final fusion information $H_{u,i}(t)$. In the fusion layer, the propagation structure features $H'(l)$, the internal emotion states $C_{u,i}(t)$ and the semantic features $F_u(i)$ are fused to obtain a final fusion information extracted from each framework (Section III-B1, III-B2, III-B3):

$$H_{u,i}(t) = H'(l) \oplus C_{u,i}(t) \oplus F_u(i) \quad (12)$$

where \oplus indicates the vector concatenating operation. Finally, the output layer for the Emo-FID is a *softmax* function to output the probabilities of false information detection and four distinct emotional region of the user.

$$P(Y_u(i)|H_{u,i}(t)) = \text{Softmax}(H_{u,i}(t) + b) \quad (13)$$

and,

$$P(S_u(i)|H_{u,i}(t)) = \text{Softmax}(VH_{u,i}(t) + b) \quad (14)$$

where $V \in R^{c \times d_w}$, and $b \in R^c$. R^c is the number of emotional regions for all u .

IV. EXPERIMENTS

In this section, we first set up our experiments and then evaluate the performance of our proposed model in comparison with several baseline models based on accuracy, precision, recall and F1 score. Then, we further conducted an ablation study to see the performance of emotion classification as part of our model.

A. Experimental Setup

1) *Dataset Description*: We evaluate our proposed method by using a publicly available Twitter dataset [36] to focus on predicting users' future emotions and false information classification by analyzing Sentiment/Emotion, Semantic, and Structural (3S) frameworks. In this dataset, the authors crawled the network and took a snapshot of the 54 million public profiles and 1.9 billion follow links in August 2009. We identified a total of 111 events (60 rumours and 51 non-rumours) from the period covered by the Twitter dataset and extracted tweets corresponding to these events based on two criteria: (i) to understand the dynamic nature of the users, a posted tweet must follow the time sequence and (ii) to

understand the dynamic emotion of the user, we filtered out from the raw datasets the users who sent 0 or only one message and tweets that did not show any emotion. The final figure after filtering comprises 14,752 users (4876 rumours and 9876 non-rumours) over a total of 1,92,359 tweets posted. Given the sequence of u 's emotion, we split the data into 90% of training and the remaining 10% as test dataset according to the temporal sequence.

2) *Evaluation Methods*: To evaluate the performance of our Emo-FID model, we compare it with four state-of-the-art baselines, including:

- DTC [37]: A traditional method based on a decision tree classifier with handcrafted features to identify the credibility of microblog posts related to trending topics.
- SVM-RBF [38]: An SVM-based model with a Radial Basis Function (RBF) kernel that uses handcrafted features based on the overall statistics of the posts.
- RvNN [39]: A tree-structured recursive neural network with GRU units captures the structural patterns of top-down and bottom-up rumour propagation trees.
- Bi-GCN [34]: A GCN-based rumour detection model utilises the Bi-directional propagation structure and dispersion characteristics.
- DynGCN [40]: A graph convolutional network-based model with attention mechanisms to capture dynamic propagation structure for rumour detection.

B. Experimental Results

TABLE I
PERFORMANCE COMPARISON BETWEEN THE EMO-FID WITH OTHER RUMOUR DETECTION METHODS (R: RUMOUR; N: NON-RUMOUR)

Method	Class	Acc.	Prec.	Rec.	F ₁
DTC	R	0.830	0.845	0.812	0.830
	N		0.815	0.825	0.821
SVM-RBF	R	0.852	0.762	0.645	0.692
	N		0.545	0.694	0.597
RvNN	R	0.897	0.898	0.886	0.895
	N		0.889	0.901	0.898
Bi-GCN	R	0.951	0.952	0.938	0.948
	N		0.942	0.945	0.946
DynGCN	R	0.956	0.942	0.961	0.952
	N		0.963	0.942	0.957
Emo-FID	R	0.971	0.966	0.973	0.969
	N		0.974	0.968	0.970

1) *Overall Performance*: Table I presents the results of our proposed model and the baselines on the Twitter dataset. According to the results shown in the Table I, we observe that our proposed model significantly achieves better performance than other baseline models in all evaluation metrics. In our first observation, deep learning-based methods (RvNN, Bi-GCN, DynGCN) performed significantly better for rumour detection than traditional machine learning-based hand-crafted methods (DTC, SVM-RBF), since these models can utilize temporal features. Significantly, in the case of Bi-GCN and DynGCN,

it performs better results than RvNN. The RvNN-based model focuses on capturing the tree-based rumour propagation structure using the leaf nodes' hidden feature vector. Unlike RvNN, the root feature enhancement allows the proposed method to pay more attention to the information of the source posts, which helps to improve the graph-based model. However, our final observation depicts that our proposal achieves an overall accuracy of 97.1%, indicating that it is essential to learn sentiment/emotional information, temporal dynamic structure and semantic information for rumour detection. Compared with the state-of-the-art methods, our proposed model achieves an accuracy improvement of 2% and 1.5% concerning Bi-GCN and DynGCN.

TABLE II
PERFORMANCE COMPARISON BETWEEN THE EMO-FID WITH OTHER COMPONENTS

Method	Acc.	Prec.	Rec.	F ₁
GRU	0.921	0.928	0.915	0.925
GCN	0.933	0.935	0.931	0.934
BERT	0.954	0.952	0.959	0.953
Emo-FID	0.971	0.965	0.969	0.969

2) *Ablation Study*: To demonstrate the model's effectiveness, we conduct a component analysis involving various modules of the model. Table II shows that the temporal dynamics structure performs better for identifying emotional information in social conversation. For instance, the GRU mechanism helps analyze the user's historical information throughout the social conversation. Similarly, the GCN method is very useful for capturing the features of propagation structures. Most importantly, the BERT mechanism is more useful for extracting sentiment and semantic information in the rumour detection task. Therefore, the experimental results and analyses prove the benefits of amalgamating all the mechanisms together to enhance the performance of our model for better identifying the user's emotions and rumour detection tasks.

V. CONCLUSION

This paper proposes an emotionally infused model, i.e., Emo-FID, to classify the user's emotion and also detect false information on social networks. Our proposed model has the ability to systematically examine temporal propagation features, different emotional influence patterns and semantic feature information. The experimental results demonstrate that our approaches outperform state-of-the-art baselines by very large margins in terms of both accuracy and efficiency. However, We believe there is still room for improvement in the context of GCNs variants and additional features from different contexts.

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REFERENCES

- [1] S. Zannettou, M. Sirivianos, J. Blackburn, and N. Kourtellis, "The web of false information: Rumors, fake news, hoaxes, clickbait, and various other shenanigans," *Journal of Data and Information Quality (JDIQ)*, vol. 11, no. 3, pp. 1–37, 2019.
- [2] M. A. Alonso, D. Vilares, C. Gómez-Rodríguez, and J. Vilares, "Sentiment analysis for fake news detection," *Electronics*, vol. 10, no. 11, p. 1348, 2021.
- [3] W. Dong, J. Tao, X. Xia, L. Ye, H. Xu, P. Jiang, and Y. Liu, "Public emotions and rumors spread during the covid-19 epidemic in china: web-based correlation study," *Journal of Medical Internet Research*, vol. 22, no. 11, p. e21933, 2020.
- [4] F. Zollo, P. K. Novak, M. Del Vicario, A. Bessi, I. Mozetič, A. Scala, G. Caldarelli, and W. Quattrociocchi, "Emotional dynamics in the age of misinformation," *PloS one*, vol. 10, no. 9, p. e0138740, 2015.
- [5] G. K. Shahi, A. Dirkson, and T. A. Majchrzak, "An exploratory study of covid-19 misinformation on twitter," *Online social networks and media*, vol. 22, p. 100104, 2021.
- [6] S. Loomba, A. De Figueiredo, S. J. Piatek, K. De Graaf, and H. J. Larson, "Measuring the impact of covid-19 vaccine misinformation on vaccination intent in the uk and usa," *Nature human behaviour*, vol. 5, no. 3, pp. 337–348, 2021.
- [7] A. H. Alamoodi, B. B. Zaidan, A. A. Zaidan, O. S. Albahri, K. I. Mohammed, R. Q. Malik, E. M. Almahdi, M. A. Chyad, Z. Tareq, A. S. Albahri *et al.*, "Sentiment analysis and its applications in fighting covid-19 and infectious diseases: A systematic review," *Expert systems with applications*, vol. 167, p. 114155, 2021.
- [8] C. G. Horner, D. Galletta, J. Crawford, and A. Shirsat, "Emotions: The unexplored fuel of fake news on social media," *Journal of Management Information Systems*, vol. 38, no. 4, pp. 1039–1066, 2021.
- [9] Z. Liu, T. Zhang, K. Yang, P. Thompson, Z. Yu, and S. Ananiadou, "Emotion detection for misinformation: A review," *Information Fusion*, p. 102300, 2024.
- [10] R. N. Zaeem, C. Li, and K. S. Barber, "On sentiment of online fake news," in *2020 IEEE/ACM International Conference on Advances in Social Networks Analysis and Mining (ASONAM)*, Online, 2020, pp. 760–767.
- [11] X. Zhou, K. Shu, V. V. Phoha, H. Liu, and R. Zafarani, "'this is fake! shared it by mistake': Assessing the intent of fake news spreaders," in *Proceedings of the ACM Web Conference 2022*, 2022, pp. 3685–3694.
- [12] C. Wang, B. Zhou, H. Tu, and Y. Liu, "Rumor detection on social media using temporal dynamic structure and emotional information," in *2021 IEEE Sixth International Conference on Data Science in Cyberspace (DSC)*. IEEE, 2021, pp. 16–22.
- [13] X. Zhang, Y. Pan, X. Gu, and G. Liang, "Sentiment analysis-based social network rumor detection model with bi-directional graph convolutional networks," in *International Conference on Computer Application and Information Security (ICCAIS 2022)*, vol. 12609. SPIE, 2023, pp. 463–469.
- [14] N. Pröllochs, D. Bär, and S. Feuerriegel, "Emotions explain differences in the diffusion of true vs. false social media rumors," *Scientific Reports*, vol. 11, no. 1, p. 22721, 2021.
- [15] S. Suntuwal, S. Brown, and M. Patton, "How does information spread? an exploratory study of true and fake news," in *Proceedings of the 53rd Hawaii International Conference on System Sciences*, Honolulu, Hawaii, 2020, pp. 5893–5902.
- [16] A. Choudhry, I. Khatri, M. Jain, and D. K. Vishwakarma, "An emotion-aware multitask approach to fake news and rumor detection using transfer learning," *IEEE Transactions on Computational Social Systems*, vol. 11, no. 1, pp. 588–599, 2024.
- [17] B. Ghanem, S. P. Ponzetto, P. Rosso, and F. Rangel, "Fakeflow: Fake news detection by modeling the flow of affective information," in *Proceedings of the 16th Conference of the European Chapter of the Association for Computational Linguistics: Main Volume*, Online, 2021, pp. 679–689.
- [18] X. Miao, D. Rao, and Z. Jiang, "Syntax and sentiment enhanced bert for earliest rumor detection," in *Natural Language Processing and Chinese Computing: 10th CCF International Conference, NLPCC 2021, Qingdao, China, October 13–17, 2021, Proceedings, Part I 10*. Springer, 2021, pp. 570–582.
- [19] H. Zhang, Z. Li, S. Liu, T. Huang, Z. Ni, J. Zhang, and Z. Lv, "Do sentence-level sentiment interactions matter? sentiment mixed heterogeneous network for fake news detection," *IEEE Transactions on Computational Social Systems*, 2023.
- [20] A. S. Hosseini and S. Staab, "Emotional framing in the spreading of false and true claims," in *Proceedings of the 15th ACM Web Science Conference 2023*, Austin, TX, USA, 2023, pp. 96–106.
- [21] B. E. Ashforth and F. Mael, "Social identity theory and the organization," *Academy of management review*, vol. 14, no. 1, pp. 20–39, 1989.
- [22] C. Chen, Z. Wang, and W. Li, "Tracking dynamics of opinion behaviors with a content-based sequential opinion influence model," *IEEE Transactions on Affective Computing*, vol. 11, no. 4, pp. 627–639, 2018.
- [23] B. Guo, Y. Ding, L. Yao, Y. Liang, and Z. Yu, "The future of false information detection on social media: New perspectives and trends," *ACM Computing Surveys (CSUR)*, vol. 53, no. 4, pp. 1–36, 2020.
- [24] X. Zhou and R. Zafarani, "A survey of fake news: Fundamental theories, detection methods, and opportunities," *ACM Computing Surveys (CSUR)*, vol. 53, no. 5, pp. 1–40, 2020.
- [25] J. Zhao, Z. Zhao, L. Shi, Z. Kuang, and Y. Liu, "Collaborative mixture-of-experts model for multi-domain fake news detection," *Electronics*, vol. 12, no. 16, p. 3440, 2023.
- [26] A. Radford, J. W. Kim, C. Hallacy, A. Ramesh, G. Goh, S. Agarwal, G. Sastry, A. Askell, P. Mishkin, J. Clark *et al.*, "Learning transferable visual models from natural language supervision," in *International conference on machine learning*. PMLR, 2021, pp. 8748–8763.
- [27] I. Kelk, B. Basseri, W. Lee, R. Qiu, and C. Tanner, "Automatic fake news detection: Are current models 'fact-checking' or 'gut-checking'?" in *Proceedings of the Fifth Fact Extraction and Verification Workshop (FEVER)*. Dublin, Ireland: Association for Computational Linguistics, 2022, pp. 29–36.
- [28] B. Ghanem, S. P. Ponzetto, P. Rosso, and F. Rangel, "Fakeflow: Fake news detection by modeling the flow of affective information," in *Proceedings of the 16th Conference of the European Chapter of the Association for Computational Linguistics: Main Volume, EACL 2021, Online, April 19 - 23, 2021*. Association for Computational Linguistics, 2021, pp. 679–689.
- [29] B. Ghanem, P. Rosso, and F. Rangel, "An emotional analysis of false information in social media and news articles," *ACM Transactions on Internet Technology (TOIT)*, vol. 20, no. 2, pp. 1–18, 2020.
- [30] L. Fang, K. Feng, K. Zhao, A. Hu, and T. Li, "Unsupervised rumor detection based on propagation tree vac," *IEEE Transactions on Knowledge and Data Engineering*, vol. 35, no. 10, pp. 10309–10323, 2023.
- [31] J. A. Russell, "A circumplex model of affect," *Journal of personality and social psychology*, vol. 39, no. 6, p. 1161, 1980.
- [32] M. M. Bradley and P. J. Lang, "Affective norms for english words (anew): Affective ratings of words and instruction manual," *University of Florida, Gainesville. FL Technical Report C-2*, vol. 41, 2010.
- [33] S. Mohammad and P. Turney, "Emotions evoked by common words and phrases: Using Mechanical Turk to create an emotion lexicon," in *Proceedings of the NAACL HLT 2010 Workshop on Computational Approaches to Analysis and Generation of Emotion in Text*. Los Angeles, CA: ACL, 2010, pp. 26–34.
- [34] T. Bian, X. Xiao, T. Xu, P. Zhao, W. Huang, Y. Rong, and J. Huang, "Rumor detection on social media with bi-directional graph convolutional networks," in *Proceedings of the AAAI conference on artificial intelligence*, vol. 34, no. 01, 2020, pp. 549–556.
- [35] Y. Rong, W. Huang, T. Xu, and J. Huang, "Dropedge: Towards deep graph convolutional networks on node classification," *arXiv preprint arXiv:1907.10903*, 2019.
- [36] S. Kwon, M. Cha, and K. Jung, "Rumor detection over varying time windows," *PloS one*, vol. 12, no. 1, p. e0168344, 2017.
- [37] C. Castillo, M. Mendoza, and B. Poblete, "Information credibility on twitter," in *Proceedings of the 20th international conference on World wide web*, 2011, pp. 675–684.
- [38] F. Yang, Y. Liu, X. Yu, and M. Yang, "Automatic detection of rumor on sina weibo," in *Proceedings of the ACM SIGKDD workshop on mining data semantics*, 2012, pp. 1–7.
- [39] J. Ma, W. Gao, and K.-F. Wong, "Rumor detection on twitter with tree-structured recursive neural networks." Association for Computational Linguistics, 2018.
- [40] J. Choi, T. Ko, Y. Choi, H. Byun, and C.-k. Kim, "Dynamic graph convolutional networks with attention mechanism for rumor detection on social media," *PloS one*, vol. 16, no. 8, p. e0256039, 2021.